

Some New Organo-Mercurials as Multipurpose Pesticides

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Some unmercurated and mercurated methoxychlor analogues of aniline bases have been synthesised by coupling one and two moles of unmercurated and mercurated diazotised substituted aniline bases, with one mole of 2,2-bis-*p*-methoxy-phenyl-1:1:1-trichloroethane (methoxychlor) with the object of testing their multipurpose pesticidal properties against insects, fungi and bacteria of agricultural importance. Seventy such compounds were tested in the laboratory against a common grain storage pest *Sitophylus oryzae*; three common pathogenic fungi *A. niger*, *C. gobossum* and *R. solani* and two bacteria, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by bio-assay methods. Mercuration, size of the diazoaniline molecule, the nature and position of the substituent, containing $\text{NO}_2\text{-CH}_3$ and $\text{NO}_2\text{-OCH}_3$ groups, in association with the moderate mercuration are some of the factors responsible for conferring potent toxicity to the three types of tested pathogens.

NEED for development of suitable and effective broad-spectrum multi-purpose pesticides is being largely felt in modern agriculture for protection against diseases and pests particularly in the cultivation of high-yielding varieties of crops. Emphasis in the past has been largely on development of specific single purpose plant protectants, useful either as fungicide, bactericide or insecticide. The multicidal action in agricultural chemicals can greatly reduce cost and also confer ease in operational schedules. The combined fungicidal and bactericidal properties exhibited by some new organo-tin compounds, reported earlier (Mehrotra and Dey^{1,2}), led the authors to extend investigations on tailoring the three chief pesticidal characters in single compounds. Since organo-mercurials are known for their combined antifungal and bactericidal properties combining them with a potent insecticidal base offered the desired ground level potential. Mildner *et al.*³, Newson⁴ and subsequently Winteringham⁵ reported antifungal and anti-inhibitory properties of a large number of organo-mercury compounds. In the selection of the insecticides for this purpose, an eye was kept for chemicals which were known to be comparatively free from human or animal toxicity. DDT, either as such, or as its numerous analogues or complexes, including DDD, DDF, DFDT and methoxychlor, with their common trade names like chlordan, aldrin, toxaphan, etc. have been extensively used as very potent insecticides. However, all these compounds, with the exception of methoxychlor and its derivatives, are known to be very toxic to animals and human beings.

Methoxychlor and its derivatives were, therefore selected as the base for introducing safe insecticidal properties in the compounds reported in this paper.

Mercurated or unmercurated diazoanilines, which have established their fungicidal-cum-bactericidal characters (Vishnoi⁶) were combined with methoxychlor. Condensation was effected with both one and two moles of unmercurated and mercurated diazotised aniline bases and one mole of methoxychlor. Following general reaction was involved:

(A) *Unmercurated series*

(B) *Mercurated series*

In case of mercurated anilines—AcOHg group occupies *o* or *p* position in the above aniline nuclei and the resultant compounds were azo-R-AcOHg-benzene in place of azo-R-benzene nuclei.

Uni-molar complexes were prepared by diazotising 0.02 moles of unmercurated or mercurated aniline bases in their hydrochloric or acetic acid solutions respectively with 0.02 moles of sodium-nitrite solutions in a freezing bath under constant mechanical stirring. The diazotised solutions so formed were trickled into cooled solutions of 0.02 mole of methoxychlor, dissolved in 200 ml of 20% sodium hydroxide solution, in another freezing bath. The reaction was completed under constant mechanical stirring which was extended to another 1 hr. The separated unmercurated methoxychlor analogues of anilines were filtered, dried and recrystallised in ethanol or acetone depending on their solubility. Complexes containing two moles of aniline bases were prepared by diazotising their double quantities in the same volume of hydrochloric and acetic acid. The isolated compounds were examined for their physical and chemical properties. Their structures were confirmed through the determinations of mercury and chlorine contents by the methods of Lomholt and Christiansen⁷ and Pirias⁸.

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A Unmercurated Series

Pesticidal action was determined by bioassay method of Loo⁹, using Potato Dextrose Agar media for fungicidal test and Agar solidified nutrient broth media for bactericidal character details of which have been reported earlier (Mehrotra and Dey^{1,2}). Fungicidal tests were made against three important fungi viz., *Aspergillus niger*, *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* and bactericidal tests on two important bacteria viz., *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Insecticidal characters were also determined by bioassay method adopted by Pradhan¹⁰ using *Sitophilus oryzae* (storage grain weevil) extensively damaging wheat grains). The details of the method were as follows :

Certain quantities of the synthesised compounds were individually dissolved in 100 ml acetone and filtered on a sintered glass funnel. The concentration of the dissolved compounds was determined by evaporating a known volume of the filtrate on a weighed watch glass and recording its final weight from which concentration of solute per ml. was worked out. These solutions were taken in gradually ascending quantities in petri-dishes and acetone allowed to be evaporate. A blank was also run simultaneously, 100 insects were subsequently taken in each petri-dish and covered immediately. The dish was kept closed for 24 hr and the number of dead insects counted thereafter. Percentage mortality was calculated for each concentration of the compound in the petri-dish. The observed and the corrected mortality obtained for different concentration of each compound in all the four series were statistically analysed by Probit analysis technique suggested by Goulden¹¹ and regression equations, LC 50, and fiducial limits worked out. Relative toxicity (RT) of all the compounds were also calculated keeping the compound with highest fiducial limit as the standard which gives unit relative toxicity.

Description and names of the compounds prepared for the four series, together with their physical and

chemical properties, is given in Table 1. The results of pesticidal bio-assay testing for their insecticidal, fungicidal and bactericidal characters are summarised in Table 2. The values of insecticidal character viz., lethal concentrations, have been expressed as mg.; while those of fungicidal and bactericidal characters in terms of zone of inhibition in mm affected by different compounds. The pesticidal potentials of these compounds are discussed in paragraphs following the tables.

The structure of the compounds synthesised was verified through quantitative estimation of mercury and chlorine which tallied fairly well with the theoretical contents. The structure of the diazo-anilines has already been established by Saxena¹² and subsequently by Vishnoi⁶ who in their studies utilized them for coupling with substituted phenols. In the present case the diazo-anilines of known structures were reacted with 2,2-bis-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1:1:1-trichloro-ethane (methoxychlor) and the coupling could take place only at the unoccupied para position of the benzene ring of the latter compound. The structure was confirmed through elemental analysis.

Physical and chemical properties of the compounds, shown in Table 1, exhibit marked variations in their melting point, colour and in contents of chlorine and mercury (in mercurated series only).

In regard to their pesticidal properties (Table 2) it is evident that this is largely affected by the nature of substituents, number of molecules of reactants and the extent of mercuration. Besides, many of the prepared compounds possess multi-pesticidal characters. As insecticide, the mercurated compounds, in unimolar series, have proved more toxic to *Sitophilus oryzae* than the corresponding unmercurated ones. Increase in mercury content, as in mercurated compounds of 2 moles methoxychlor analogues of aniline, failed to show further rise in toxicity, even

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF UNMERCURATED AND MERCURATED METHOXYCHLOR ANALOGUES OF ANILINE

Properties/ Nature of R	1 mole DAB+1 mole MC				2 moles DAB+1 mole MC			
	M.P.°C	Colour	Chlorine %	Mercury %	M.P.°C	Colour	Chlorine %	Mercury %
-NH ₂	245	G	23.4	—	234	GY	19.0	—
2-CH ₃	263	DY	22.5	—	243	DG	18.0	—
3-CH ₃	260	DY	22.5	—	240	WG	18.0	—
2-OC ₂ H ₅	212	GY	21.3	—	218	CY	16.2	—
4-OC ₂ H ₅	232	DY	21.0	—	261	LB	16.1	—
2-OCH ₃	202	DR	22.0	—	232	RB	17.1	—
3-OCH ₃	223	DR	22.6	—	178	GR	17.0	—
3-NO ₂ -6-CH ₃	267	YO	20.3	—	250	BC	15.4	—
3-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃	225	CY	22.0	—	165	BR	14.6	—
4-CH ₃ -6-NO ₂	229	M	20.5	—	267	RB	15.6	—
3-Cl-6-CH ₃	230	F	28.4	—	212	DY	27.0	—
4-Cl-6-CH ₃	237	WY	28.2	—	240	RF	27.0	—
4-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃	216	OR	20.0	—	213	LY	14.3	—
2-Cl	238	DG	29.0	—	230	C	20.1	—
3-Cl	240	CB	29.0	—	220	LG	28.2	—
2-NO ₂	235	DY	21.1	—	195	BY	16.0	—
4-NO ₂	215	DO	21.1	—	242	DY	16.2	—
Nature of R	1 mole mercurated DAB+1 mole MC				2 moles mercurated DAB+1 mole MC			
NH ₂ -4-AcOHg	255	LY	14.7	28.0	232	LY	9.5	36.0
2CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	260	LY	13.7	27.3	240	LG	9.3	36.1
3CH ₃ -2-4-AcOHg	240	GY	11.0	40.5	250	YG	6.3	49.0
-2CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	235	M	14.1	26.8	262	R	9.0	35.0
3OCH ₃ -4-AcOHg	242	OR	14.0	26.9	245	LR	8.8	35.1
4-OCH ₃ -2-AcOHg	233	R	14.0	26.7	183	LY	9.0	34.9
2-OC ₂ H ₅ -4-AcOHg	203	CB	13.7	26.4	265	F	9.0	34.1
4-OC ₂ H ₅ -2-AcOHg	247	F	13.8	26.0	267	YF	8.6	34.2
3-NO ₂ -6-CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	240	RO	18.6	25.7	220	Y	8.6	33.2
3-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃ -4AcOHg	237	DR	13.1	25.5	267	DY	8.6	32.5
2-Cl-4-AcOHg	213	DY	19.0	26.6	245	LG	15.2	34.6
3-Cl-4-AcOHg	245	RO	19.0	26.4	255	WG	15.1	34.8
4-CH ₃ -6-NO ₂ :2AcOHg	260	OR	13.3	25.7	258	M	8.6	33.0
4-Cl-6-CH ₃ -2-AcOHg	220	DY	18.6	25.8	243	DF	15.0	33.7
3-Cl-6-CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	252	YR	18.5	26.0	259	RO	15.4	34.0
4-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃ -2AcOHg	218	DY	13.4	25.0	263	RO	8.4	32.4
2NO ₂ -4AcOHg	189	R	13.9	26.0	246	LY	9.0	34.2
4NO ₂ -2AcOHg	220	CR	13.8	26.2	240	DC	8.8	34.3

DAB = Diazotised aniline bases, MC = Methoxychlor, G = Grey, Y = Yellow, R = Red, C = Chocolate, O = Orange, F = Fawn, M = Maroon, B = Brown, L = Light, D = Dark, W = Whitish.

TABLE 2—PESTICIDAL PROPERTIES OF UNMERCURATED AND MERCURATED DIAZOTISED ANILINES METHOXYCHLORS

Properties Compounds, Nature of R	Insecticidal				Fungicidal		Bactericidal	
	1 mole DAB+ 1 mole MC		2 moles DAB+ 1 mole MC		1 mole DAB+1 mole MC	2 moles DAB+1 mole MC	1 mole DAB+1 mole MC	2 moles DAB+1 mole MC
	LC50 mg/ml	RT	LC50 mg/ml	RT	mm	mm	mm	mm
<i>Unmercurated</i>								
-NH ₂	5.36	1.93	10.16	1.00	77.1	8.6	8.5	8.7
2-CH ₃	8.20	1.26	4.05	2.51	9.3	8.8	10.0	10.0
3-CH ₃	7.58	1.36	5.89	1.72	11.3	8.6	10.5	11.7
2-OC ₂ H ₅	1.92	5.38	5.78	1.76	10.3	7.4	10.5	9.0
4-OC ₂ H ₅	1.85	5.58	5.85	1.74	10.0	11.5	11.0	8.0
2-OCH ₃	5.40	1.91	7.26	1.40	7.2	10.1	6.5	12.5
3-OCH ₃	5.35	1.93	7.10	1.43	8.2	8.3	8.0	7.5
3-NO ₂ -6-CH ₃	2.41	4.29	6.21	1.64	11.3	11.5	10.5	10.0
3-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃	7.53	1.37	4.99	2.04	12.2	11.0	6.2	12.2
4-CH ₃ -6-NO ₂	7.72	1.34	9.57	1.06	6.0	13.8	6.5	13.9
3-Cl-6-CH ₃	7.24	1.41	9.28	1.09	6.5	13.0	8.9	12.0
4-Cl ₃ -6-CH ₃	8.04	1.28	6.37	1.59	8.5	8.3	7.8	6.6
4-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃	9.44	1.09	6.34	1.60	11.3	14.0	11.4	12.8
2-Cl	7.79	1.33	5.05	2.01	10.9	7.1	7.4	11.7
3-Cl	10.24	1.01	7.36	1.38	7.5	7.1	5.5	7.2
2-NO ₂	6.49	1.59	7.59	1.34	13.3	7.5	9.5	6.2
4-NO ₂	10.33	1.00	6.32	1.61	10.5	10.0	12.2	10.0
<i>Mercurated</i>								
Nature of R								
-NH ₂ -4-AcOHg	3.01	5.80	6.05	1.54	10.0	10.6	10.0	9.7
2CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	8.11	2.15	9.35	1.00	9.6	11.0	11.5	10.5
3CH ₃ -2,4-AcOHg	5.75	3.03	7.52	1.24	9.0	8.6	10.5	9.5
2-OCH ₃ -4-AcOHg	9.44	1.85	7.46	1.25	11.5	7.1	13.5	10.5
3-OCH ₃ -4-AcOHg	12.72	1.43	6.95	1.35	11.3	10.0	7.5	7.5
4-OCH ₃ -2-AcOHg	11.58	1.50	7.84	1.20	8.5	7.0	8.4	8.7
2-OC ₂ H ₅ -4-AcOHg	6.24	2.80	8.12	1.15	11.5	8.8	12.0	7.5
4-OC ₂ H ₅ -2-AcOHg	4.73	3.68	8.63	1.09	13.3	14.3	15.5	14.0
3-NO ₂ -6-3H ₃ -4-AcOHg	2.36	7.37	8.43	1.11	12.8	14.0	13.8	14.0
3-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃ -4-AcOHg	5.72	3.05	3.78	2.47	15.2	11.3	13.0	14.0
2-Cl-4-AcOHg	7.44	2.34	5.90	1.58	8.8	10.0	10.8	9.0
3-Cl-4-AcOHg	7.51	2.32	8.67	1.08	6.3	8.6	7.3	4.7
4-CH ₃ -6-NO ₂ -2-AcOHg	2.10	8.30	3.89	2.40	11.8	15.0	12.8	13.5
4-Cl-6-CH ₃ -2-AcOHg	1.82	9.57	2.05	4.56	14.4	15.0	14.8	11.2
3-Cl-6-CH ₃ -4-AcOHg	-2.06	8.41	2.24	4.17	8.6	5.8	9.1	7.7
4-NO ₂ -6-OCH ₃ -2-AcOHg	17.43	1.00	5.57	1.68	8.2	8.9	5.8	11.5
2-NO ₂ -4-AcOHg	11.90	1.46	6.90	1.35	9.3	9.1	11.0	10.2
4-NO ₂ -2-AcOHg	11.62	1.50	7.24	1.29	9.6	10.1	8.9	11.0

though they maintain their superiority against corresponding unmercurated compounds. Individually, compounds containing $O-C_2H_5$ groups, at ortho and para positions, and $3-NO_2-6-CH_3$ groups, in unimolar unmercurated series, exhibit marked toxicity to the insect in descending order. The bimolar compounds, of similar series, show best toxicity in cases where $2-CH_3$, $3NO_2-6-OCH_3$, $2-Cl$ and $2-OC_2H_5$ groups are present in the diazo aniline nuclei. Mercuration improved the toxicity even in the above series particularly those having $4-Cl-6CH_3$ etc.

For fungicidal properties of these compounds it was found that both unmercurated and mercurated methoxychlor analogues of aniline are toxic to three fungi under test and that increase in size of molecule or mercuration further helps in the enhancement of this character. In unimolar series of unmercurated compounds, the substituents containing $2-NO_2$, $3NO_2-6-OCH_3$ and $4-NO_2-6-OCH_3$ and $3NO_2-6-CH_3$ groups, were more fungitoxic than the rest. Increasing the size of the molecule through prolonged diazotisation and mercuration has centralised the fungitoxic characters, rather more sharply, in compounds containing $3-NO_2-6-OCH_3$, $4Cl-6-CH_3-4-OC_2H_5$ and $3NO_2-6CH_3$ groups. Further increase in mercury content, as in bimolar combinations, impart greater fungitoxicity to these compounds the most toxic ones being those which have $4-CH_3-6NO_2$, $4Cl-6CH_3-4-OC_2H_5$ and $3NO_2-6CH_3$ groups in the diazoaniline nuclei.

Size of molecule in unmercurated group and mercuration in unimolar series have largely influenced and bactericidal properties of these new compounds. But increased mercuration has failed to record further improvement in this behaviour. Singly, in unimolar series, substituents such as $4-NO_2$, $4-NO_2-6-OCH_3$ and $4-OC_2H_5$ and in bimolar ones the substituents $4-CH_3-6-NO_2$, $4-NO_2-6-OCH_3$, $2-OCH_3$ and $3NO_2-6-OCH_3$ have tended to impart maximum bactericidal action. Mercuration has shown much greater improvement in unimolar series and maximum bacteritoxicity was recorded in compounds associated with $4-OC_2H_5$, $4-Cl-6CH_3$, $3-NO_2-6-CH_3$ and $2-OCH_3$ groups; but in bimolar series highest bactericidal action was found in compound having $2-$ or $4-OC_2H_5$ and $3NO_2-6-CH_3$ and $4CH_3-6NO_2$ or $4-NO_2-6-OCH_3$ groups in the nuclei.

Altogether, the entire bio-assay data highlights the selective effect of factors like size of the diazoaniline nuclei, mercuration and the nature and position of substituents on the overall pesticidal properties of

methoxychlor analogues of aniline. A proper manipulative combination of these offer compounds of wide potential use as plant protectants with multi-cidal action. Particularly the compounds, containing $2-$ or $4-OC_2H_5$ and $3NO_2-6-OCH_3$ groups in unmercurated methoxychlor analogues of aniline, can become a mono chemical for combined use as fungicide and bactericide. In summary, it can be stated that the position of NO_2-OCH_3 groups in the nuclei materially influences the pesticidal character. CH_3 groups at ortho or meta positions impart insecticidal or fungicidal properties while $-Cl$ group confers only insecticidal characters. A $-NO_2$ group at the ortho position imparts fungicidal while one at the para position confers marked bactericidal characters.

Mercuration of methoxychlor analogues of aniline impart marked pesticidal characters to the compounds. Here again compounds containing $-CH_3$ or $-OCH_3$ groups in combination with $-NO_2$ groups at suitable positions $3-NO_2-6-OCH_3$; $3-NO_2-6-OCH_3$ and $6-NO_2-4-CH_3$ exhibit remarkable multi-purpose toxicity against all the three pathogens including insect, fungi and bacteria. Compounds containing $4Cl-6CH_3$ groups also possess multipesticidal properties. Mercurated compounds with $4-OC_2H_5$ groups impart fungicidal and bactericidal properties while $3-Cl-CH_3$ groups assign them insecticidal characteristics.

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